

Unlocking Engagement: A Case Study on Virtual Field Trips in Higher Education

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Keywords: Virtual Field Trips, No-Code App Development, Student Engagement

STRUCTURED ABSTRACT

Aim of the contribution

The research aims to uncover how a virtual field trip (VFT) impacts student engagement for a population of students from diverse backgrounds that are majority low-income. Educators can promote equity by making field trips more accessible for students from diverse backgrounds using VFTs. This paper details the process of developing a VFT app and includes app screenshots, serving as a resource for faculty interested in adopting VFTs.

Value of the contribution

A valuable contribution of this research is highlighting the impact of VFTs on student engagement. Additionally, educators will learn how to integrate VFTs into their curriculum using an open-source platform for developing a VFT app. This tool is easy for faculty to use since no coding skills are required. By distributing the VFT app as a freely available Open Educational Resource (OER), educators can bridge equity gaps, benefiting students from low-income and underserved groups (Barrientos, 2022; Beile et al., 2020; DeNoyelles & Raible, 2021; Lebens, 2021).

Research outline

Research context

This research paper investigates the impact of the "ZooCoder" VFT app on student engagement in a software development course. ZooCoder, designed to teach database and programming principles, immerses students in a virtual visit to the Como Zoo, located in Saint Paul, MN, USA. The app employs Google Maps and GPS coordinates to virtually guide students to landmarks within the zoo. During this experience, students

learn to create a simple relational database to track feeding schedules for the zoo animals and develop a web application that allows the zookeepers to view the schedules.

There are numerous learning benefits that VFTs provide, such as active learning, knowledge gains, scaffolding, flexibility, and higher student engagement. Research demonstrates active learning enhances student outcomes (Chen & Liu, 2021; Freeman et al., 2014). Engaging in VFTs leads to significant gains in knowledge while minimizing cognitive load (Alazmi & Alemtairy, 2024; Mead et al., 2019). Well-designed VFTs provide flexibility and scaffold conceptual challenges (Abdallah et al., 2023; Kim et al., 2021). VFTs utilize real-life scenarios to motivate student interest and increase engagement (Lebens, 2022; Ruberto et al., 2023). In addition to the learning benefits of VFTs, VFTs promote equity by overcoming barriers of traditional field trips that impact low-income students, such as cost and lack of transportation (Dawkins & Young, 2020; Feig et al., 2019; Harron et al., 2019; Kobayashi, 2017; Ruberto, 2018; Shinneman et al., 2020).

Problem, overall research aims, and research questions

This research addresses the problem of how to increase student engagement and the aim is to explore if a VFT increases student engagement, specifically for students from diverse backgrounds. The research questions are:

R1: How do virtual field trips impact student engagement?

R2: Do students from a diverse, majority low-income population perceive the OER virtual field trip app as accessible?

Design, methodology, and research approach

The study employs a descriptive case study design. The participants are students at an urban college in the United States, where a majority of students are students of color and are Pell-grant eligible. Pell grant eligibility serves as a proxy for low-income (Whelan, 2019). Students will complete a survey with both open- and closed-ended questions about their VFT experience. Descriptive statistics will be used to analyze the quantitative data from the closed-ended responses. A thematic coding approach will be employed to analyze the qualitative data from the open-ended responses.

Expected findings

The research is expected to find insights into how VFT impact student engagement and whether students in a diverse population that is majority low-income perceive an OER VFT app as accessible.

Research limitations and implications

A key limitation is the small sample size due to the pilot nature of the research. However, iterative modifications of the app coupled with a longitudinal study across multiple course sections promise valuable insights for future implementations of the study. Another limitation is the study population is primarily composed of students of color and low-income individuals. Nevertheless, the researcher aims to gain specific insights into how this student group perceives an OER VFT app, as OER has demonstrated benefits for such populations (DeRosa, 2020).

The broad implication of this research is increasing the use of virtual field trips across disciplines to enhance student engagement and promote equity, particularly for students from diverse backgrounds. This descriptive case study contributes to the ongoing dialogue about innovative teaching methods and their impact on student learning, as well as the body of research on increasing equity through OER.

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